

**VEGGIECARE: IOT-BASED VEGETABLE CARE MONITORING AND
AUTOMATED WATERING SYSTEM WITH MOBILE APP INTEGRATION****Ronald Fernandez****ORCID ID - 0009-0007-0979-6315**

Professor, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

Vhenz Ashley D. Tongson**ORCID ID - 0009-0002-9528-4992**

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

Richmon A. Vallejos**ORCID ID - 0009-0003-2604-0772**

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

Erwin Villanueva**ORCID ID - 0009-0003-0848-3529**

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

Alvin Vinarao**ORCID ID - 0009-0006-1765-8804**

UG Students, College of Computing Studies, Universidad de Manila, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The Internet of Things has caused a huge revolution in industries by collecting data in real-time, performing automation, and connecting physical things to digital systems. In agriculture this can help manage the watering for vegetables and remote monitoring through application.

The study presents VeggieCare, an IoT-Based Vegetable Care Monitoring and Automated Watering System with Mobile App Integration that aims to enhance vegetable growth through the automation of monitoring and watering. The system uses an ESP32 microcontroller interfaced with soil moisture, temperature, humidity, and light sensors. Data is transmitted to a mobile application that is using a Firebase realtime database so the user can monitor vegetable conditions, get real time updates, and automatically watered the plant using a waterpump. Predefined threshold values for different vegetable species, in conjunction with an inbuilt dictionary on care of vegetables, allowing the users to choose what vegetable they will care.

When soil moisture becomes dry or rather too dry, the system automatically activates the watering system using the water pump. With a combination of real-time monitoring and automation, VeggieCare presents a cost-effective, sustainable, and user-friendly solution to keep the vegetables healthy while minimizing the chances of overwatering or under watering.

Keywords:

Internet of Things, automation, VeggieCare, ESP32 microcontroller, soil moisture sensor, Firebase realtime database, mobile app, real-time monitoring, water pump, predefined threshold values

INTRODUCTION

The Internet of Things (IoT) is a rapidly evolving technology that transforms traditional systems by enabling smart, connected devices. It has powered innovations across sectors such as smart homes, energy optimization, industrial automation, and agriculture. IoT allows physical devices to collect, transmit, and respond to real-time data, resulting in automation and improved decision-making. IoT is being used more and more in agriculture to automate maintenance procedures and monitor environmental conditions in order to maximize plant growth.

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Veggiecare, especially for beginners and urban dwellers, can be challenging due to inconsistent watering schedules and limited environmental awareness. This is particularly true for growing vegetables, where different species require specific soil moisture levels, lighting, and temperature ranges. Many home gardeners struggle to balance care routines, leading to overwatering, underwatering, or stunted growth. Addressing these challenges requires a system that can intelligently monitor and respond to vegetable needs, even when the user is away.

To solve this, the researchers developed an IoT-based veggiecare monitoring and automated watering system focused on vegetable growth. The system is built around the ESP32 microcontroller, which gathers real-time data from various environmental sensors. This includes a capacitive soil moisture sensor, a DHT22 sensor for temperature and humidity. The ESP32 processes the data and communicates wirelessly with a mobile application, providing the user with live updates and control capabilities.

The mobile application serves as the user interface, allowing for real-time monitoring, and access to a built-in vegetable library. This library provides care information and ideal environmental conditions for different vegetable species, helping users understand the needs of the vegetables they are growing. The users can choose from various vegetable species. Once a species of vegetable is selected, the system automatically applies predefined optimal thresholds for moisture and temperature. The system includes an automated watering mechanism composed of a relay module and a mini water pump, which activates only when the soil moisture level falls below the set threshold. By incorporating IoT, predefined vegetable-specific thresholds, and user-oriented features such as the vegetable dictionary. This system aims to simplify vegetable gardening, promote healthier vegetable growth, and reduce the risk of watering errors. The integration of low-cost sensors, an efficient microcontroller, and a mobile app interface provides a cost-effective, scalable, and user-friendly solution for home-based vegetable cultivation.

OBJECTIVES

The main objective of this study is to develop an innovative Internet of Things (IoT)-based system for automated veggie care management.

1. To create an efficient, inexpensive veggiecare monitoring system based on an ESP32 microcontroller. The system shall reside in a protecting case and mounted close to a planter box, designed for indoor and outdoor use. It will collect and process data from connected environmental sensors, including a soil moisture sensor and a DHT22 sensor (for temperature and humidity).
2. To develop a simplified mobile application interface. The mobile app will enable users to track real-time sensor readings, receive notifications. It will also alert users for conditions such as dry soil.
3. To design a smart automated watering mechanism based on soil moisture levels. A small water pump (or hose/sprinkler system depending on installation) will only turn on when the soil moisture drops below a specified threshold. A delay mechanism for short durations will also be incorporated to avoid overwatering due to recurring dry readings or spurious triggers.
4. To enable scalability for multiple planting setups. The system will support at least 2–3 devices, each assigned to a planter box, vase, or outdoor planting area with one vegetable species per unit. This allows flexibility for clients to expand monitoring across various garden setups

METHODOLOGY

This chapter outlines the processes and procedures involved in the design of the ESP32-based veggiecare monitoring and automatic watering system. The chapter outlines the system design, hardware and software, implementation process, and testing procedures. The methodology is used to ensure that the system efficiently monitors environmental conditions like temperature, humidity, soil moisture, and light intensity and includes automatic and manual inputs for vegetable care functions.

Through this study, with the use of Agile the system developed through successive sprints which concentrated on feature development alongside testing and improvement. The system received ongoing feedback while enabling adaptable improvements and quick problem-solving capabilities. The system combined hardware elements (sensors, ESP32, water pump and light intensity) with software components (Flutter app, Blynk integration).

Agile Development Model Diagram

The study follows the Agile Methodology, ensuring iterative improvement and user feedback

Figure 1 Agile Development Model Diagram

Requirements Gathering

Interview: Conducted with a horticulturist to gain expert insights on vegetable care, irrigation practices, and practical guidelines for proper soil moisture management.

Observation: Carried out on existing plant watering practices to identify common inefficiencies and determine areas where automation could improve care.

Survey: Distributed to potential users to collect feedback on usability expectations, satisfaction, and willingness to adopt the system.

Research: Reviewed related studies, scientific literature, and credible online agricultural sources to establish soil moisture thresholds and support the system design

Review

In the final stage of the study, both qualitative observations from users and quantitative evaluation results were analyzed to measure the system’s effectiveness in automating vegetable care and monitoring. Iterative testing was carried out to assess the performance of the VeggieCare system in terms of sensor accuracy, mobile app responsiveness, and automated watering reliability.

Feedback from participants revealed that the system was able to provide consistent and real-time monitoring of soil moisture, temperature, humidity, and light conditions. The automated watering function, which activates the pump when soil moisture falls below the threshold, proved efficient in preventing both overwatering and underwatering. Survey responses highlighted the reliability, usability, and portability of the system, confirming its practical value for home gardening and small-scale farming.

The review also indicated opportunities for future improvements, such as expanding the vegetable care library, enhancing the user interface, and integrating additional sensors for more precise crop management. These refinements ensure that VeggieCare continues to meet its objectives of providing a sustainable, cost-effective, and user-friendly solution for vegetable care and monitoring.

Figure 2 Conceptual Framework

VeggieCare is an IoT-based system designed to automate and optimize vegetable care for small-scale gardening. To monitor soil moisture, temperature, and humidity, the system combines sensors, an ESP32 microcontroller, and a mobile application. Different vegetables have different thresholds, and the system operates on them to allow watering to take place only when needed.

The ESP32 reads sensor data and activates the water pump whenever the soil moisture drops below the required threshold. When watering is starting a buzzer serves as an alert. The system can be operated in automatic mode, where decisions are made based on predetermined thresholds. The Firebase Realtime Database is used to synchronize data and control signals, and the mobile application offers a vegetable care dictionary to help users choose the right settings for their species.

The mobile application allows users to view real-time data and access a vegetable care dictionary, which provides information on the optimal growing conditions for different vegetable species. This combination of automated monitoring, threshold-based control, and encourages healthier vegetable growth even when users are not physically present. Users can view real-time data and access a vegetable care dictionary, which offers information on the ideal growing conditions for various vegetable species

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 3 Bar Graph of the Overall Evaluation of VeggieCare

The evaluation of the “VeggieCare: IoT-Based Vegetable Care Monitoring and Automated Watering System with Mobile Application Integration” among the possible users such as plant hobbyist, plant-related professionals, and agriculture students. Using a 5-point Likert scale, with 5 as the highest and 1 as the lowest, most ratings were within the range of 4.0 (Agree) to 4.5 (Strongly Agree). Respondents confirmed that the system provided helpful tools for real-time vegetable monitoring, automated watering based on soil moisture thresholds, and a mobile app for convenience. The system was found to be easy to use, reliable in performance, and adaptable across vegetable types.

Figure 4 Functionality

This criterion was evaluated using three sub-criteria: plant monitoring features, integration with the mobile app, and system error handling. The results simply show 95% of respondents agreed that the system delivers reliable monitoring, 90% confirmed that the system integrates well with the mobile app and 85% reported that the system operates with minimal efforts.

Figure 5 Performance and Efficiency

This criterion was evaluated using three sub-criteria: mobile app loading speed, resources efficiency, and realtime data processing. The results simply show 97% of respondents agreed that the mobile app loads quickly, 90% agreed that the system uses resources efficiently without slowing down the device, and 95% confirmed that the system processes data in real time.

Figure 6 Usability

This criterion was evaluated using three sub-criteria: ease of operation, interface organization, and efficiency in reducing plant care effort. The result simply shows that 95% of respondents agreed that the system is easy to understand and operate, while 95% validated that the app interface is clear and organized, and 90% agreed that it reduces time and effort in plant care.

Figure 7 Reliability

This criterion was evaluated using three sub-criteria: stability across different conditions, accuracy of sensor readings, and system performance under continuous use. The results simply show that 90% supported that the system perform reliably under different conditions such as day, night, and hot or cold. Meanwhile, 90% validated that the sensors provide accurate and consistent readings and 95% confirmed that the app works fine even when used continuously.

Figure 8 Security

This criterion was evaluated using three sub-criteria: communication stability, safe operation, and data protection. The results simply show that 90% supported that the system ensures that device operations such as watering and monitoring cannot be triggered incorrectly. About 90% confirmed it protects plant monitoring data from loss or corruption, and 89% validated that the system continues to operate safely without being easily disrupted.

Figure 9 Maintainability

This criterion was evaluated using three sub-criteria: non-disruptive updates, updatability, and clarity of documentation. The results simply show that 90% validated that the system updates can be made without affecting other features, 95% confirmed that the system can be updated for future improvements, and 93% agreed that the documentation or user guide is clear and helpful.

Figure 10 Portability

This criterion was evaluated using three sub-criteria: operation under low internet connection, ease of installation, and consistency across environments. The results simply show that 90% of respondents agreed that the system can work even with low internet connection, 91% validated that The app is easy to install and start using. Meanwhile 87% supported that the system performs consistently in both indoor and outdoor environments.

Summary of Quantitative Evaluation

The evaluation of VeggieCare: IoT-Based Plant Care Monitoring and Automated Watering System with Mobile Application was conducted using seven major sub-characteristics of ISO/IEC 25010 in a way that best illustrated the overall quality of the system.

1. Functionality

Respondents rated the system highly for meeting plant monitoring needs, integrating with the mobile app, and watering automatically based on soil moisture thresholds. Average score: 4.50 / 5.

2. Performance Efficiency

Users noted that the app loads quickly, processes sensor data in real time, and updates without delays. Average score: 4.40 / 5.

3. Usability

The system was described as easy to use, with a clear interface, intuitive controls, and helpful instructions that reduce the effort needed for plant care. Average score: 4.30 / 5.

4. Reliability

Respondents reported that the system functioned consistently, with accurate readings and stable performance under different conditions. Average score: 4.30 / 5.

5. Security

The system was commended for preventing accidental errors, protecting plant monitoring data, and ensuring safe device operations. Average score: 4.30 / 5.

6. Maintainability

Participants indicated that the system is structured well, can be updated, and is easy to troubleshoot when needed. Average score: 4.20 / 5.

7. Portability

The system was found adaptable, performing well across locations, internet conditions, and environments. Average score: 4.20 /

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CONCLUSION

The VeggieCare: IoT-Based Vegetable Care Monitoring and Automated Watering System with Mobile App Integration has proven to be an effective smart plant care solution that integrates IoT technology with mobile applications to provide real-time monitoring and automated watering. The system was rated excellent across all evaluation criteria, particularly excelling in functional stability and efficiency. With its capability to automatically manage watering schedules based on soil moisture, VeggieCare demonstrates its potential to assist farmers, gardeners, and hobbyists in reducing manual effort and ensuring proper plant care. The study concludes that VeggieCare is a reliable, efficient, and user-accepted system that contributes to sustainable and convenient plant management practices.

REFERENCES

- 1) Alam, M., S. Rukhsar, and A. Akram. 2021. "Plant Monitoring System." *International Journal of Engineering Research & Technology (IJERT)* 10, no. 9: 1–3. <https://www.ijert.org/research/plant-monitoring-system-IJERTV10IS090003.pdf>.
- 2) Kumar, N., Anjum, S., Iqbal, M., Mohiuddin, A., Mishra, S. (2022). Indoor Plant Health Monitoring and Tracking System. In: Dehuri, S., Prasad Mishra, B.S., Mallick, P.K., Cho, SB. (eds) Biologically Inspired Techniques in Many Criteria Decision Making. Smart Innovation, Systems and Technologies, vol 271. Springer, Singapore. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-981-16-8739-6_44
- 3) Mohabuth, A. Q., & Nem, D. (2023). *An IoT-Based Model for Monitoring Plant Growth in Greenhouses*. *Journal of Information Systems and Informatics*, 5(2), 536-549. <https://doi.org/10.51519/journalisi.v5i2.489> Ramirez, J. E. G., Valerio, M. K. A., Layug, J. R., Santiago Jr, C. S., Ulanday, M. L. P., & Alabanza, J. E. (2025). Application of expert systems with artificial intelligence in the medical field: A literature review. *ASEAN Journal of Scientific and Technological Reports*, 28(2), e255684. <https://doi.org/10.55164/ajstr.v28i2.255684>
- 4) Taylor, K. C., Alvarez, M. A., & Barretto, C. J. (2024). *IoT Based Hydroponic Plant Monitoring and Sensor System*. Manuel S. Enverga University Foundation. MSEUF Research. Retrieved from <https://mseuf.edu.ph/research/read/2324>
- 5) Fadillah, F., Buatun, R., & Ramadani, S. (2023). IoT-based hydroponic plant monitoring system. *Journal of Artificial Intelligence and Engineering Applications (JAIEA)*, 3(1), 38–43. <https://doi.org/10.59934/jaiea.v3i1.255>